

Ethical and Legal Issues Guiding Peace Journalism in Nigeria

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 27 July 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Ethical Issues in Journalism Legal Issues in Journalism Peace Journalism</p>	<p>Every profession is regulated by a set of laws, code of conduct or ethics to enhance her operation. Peace journalism begun as a critical and necessary framework for responsible media practice in conflict-sensitive environments to foster peace and unity. In Nigeria, a country predisposed to ethno-religious tensions, political unrest, and insurgencies, peace journalism offers a constructive alternative to traditional conflict reporting. This article examines the ethical and legal issues that guide peace journalism in Nigeria. Drawing on existing literatures and Nigerian media regulations, the article highlights the challenges and responsibilities journalists face in promoting peace through their reporting. The paper argues that adherence to ethical standards and legal frameworks are essential for the successful implementation of peace journalism in Nigeria.) The paper concludes that peace journalism a framework that aims to report conflicts in ways that promote peace has been advocated as a solution. However, ethical and legal challenges often undermine its effectiveness is the order of the day in journalistic practice in Nigeria. This situation which presents unique ethical and legal hurdles necessitates a strong localized framework for peace journalism practice. Journalists of broadcast, print and digital media should be peace oriented when reporting conflict especially those of cross-border nature. The paper recommends constant capacity building for journalist on strict adherence to ethical, legal and professional standard. It also recommends editorial independence and adequate remuneration of journalists to avoid collection of brown envelopes which could interfere with objectivity, truth and fairness</p>

1. Introduction

Nigeria, before now, used to be a country that is richly blessed with happy people surrounded by abundant natural and mineral resources. These people have lived together in peace, harmony and in tranquility for decades. They were also very loving and caring irrespective of their differences in tribes and traditions. Their life of hospitality and tranquility which attracted many strangers in to the country reigned until it was taken for granted due to the complex socio-political scenery that is characterized by incessant clashes ranging from ethno-religious, ethnicity, consistent insurgencies in the northeast region of the country, farmers and headers in the northern part of the country. On this note, the role of the media becomes inevitable. Peace journalism on the other hand which is another aspect of journalistic practice that addresses peace related issues in the society. It is a method of journalism committed to exploring root causes of conflict in order to “create opportunities for society at large to consider and value non-violent responses to conflict” (Lynch and McGoldrick, 2005 in Zeng & Akinro, 2021). Its history can be traced back to 1965, when Johan Galtung and Mari Ruge analysed what makes foreign news newsworthy. Jake Lynch and Johan Galtung (Lynch and Galtung, 2010) later established the notion of peace journalism and argued that the media (war reporting, in particular) predominantly exhibit biases towards violence and rest on the conceptual belief that ‘conflict’ equals ‘war’. Within the field of peace journalism, this view was considered a problem because it averts conflict to be considered as an opportunity for the search of a new harmony between the parties involved, through a process that does not have to necessarily grow into a war or conflict. In fact, as Johan Galtung’s theory of nonviolence and conflict resolution suggests, a conflict is a clash of incompatible interests amongst the parties that can be transcended in order to reach a further and deeper agreement. The ethics journalism profession have today been influenced by normative philosophies of liberal theory, objectivity and social responsibility theory, interpretive theory and ethics of community and care. From the liberal theory view, journalism profession should be independent in informing citizens and be a watchdog of the government and abuses of power. The social responsibility theory states that publication must be accurate and comprehensively true on

matters of public interest. It also opines that representation of the constituents’ groups in society and assist in the presentation of goals and values of society. Interpretive and activist perspective on journalism ethics however, rejects ‘neutrality’, where journalists are compelled to take a stance and be partisans that seek societal improvement or growth thereby challenging those at the helm of affairs or the statuesque. Conflicts occur in two phases; it is either constructive or destructive, positive or negative. It is said to be constructive or positive when managed in a constructive way and the resultant effect is development, change, resolution, friendship, interaction, communication, better governance, better social organization, and social justice and destructive or negative when managed in a destructive way, and the resultant effect is violence, death, destruction of properties, environmental damage. On this not, Abimbola, O. T., & Domink, D. N. (2013) opine that the media serve as an intermediary between disputing parties, rousing report that might either be constructive or destructive, depending on what is reported. It can be constructive when it promotes greater communications between the parties thereby promoting peaceful coexistence, and destructive when it insight thereby leading to conflict, causes divide between the parties, or denigration. The use of frame to report an incident also determines the escalation, use of frames such as battle metaphor; issue dualism can escalate conflicts destructively. Media reportage on ethnicity can fuel ethnocentrism that can polarize groups or community. This is where the role of peace journalists is mostly needed where their reportage is more of fostering peace and integration. Journalists make conscious or unconscious framing judgments in deciding what to say, guided by frames that organize their belief systems via their reports. The text contains frames, which are manifested by the presence or absence of certain keywords, stock phrases, stereotyped images, sources of information, and sentences that provide thematically reinforcing clusters of facts or judgments. The frames that guide the receiver's thinking and conclusion may or may not reflect the frames in the text and the framing intention of the journalist. The culture is the stock of commonly invoked frames. Framing by media can decide the direction the conflict takes. According to McLaughlin (2018) “intractable disputes are usually associated

with a complex and reinforcing set of frames about oneself, the others, risks, what information should apply to the situation, and how decisions should be made." They put forward six frames that are usually applicable to intractable disputes: identity frame, characterization frame, power frame, conflict management/process frame, risk/information frame, and loss versus gain frame. Gultang presents a two-way approach of looking at a conflict: the high road and the low road. In the low road approach media views conflict as a battle where the parties involved are usually reduced to the number 2, who are opponents in a struggle to impose their respective goals. The underlying reporting model is that of "a military command: who advances, who capitulates short of their goals; counting the losses in terms of nos. killed, wounded, and material damage." The zero-sum perspective draws upon sports reporting where "winning is not the only thing, but everything". The high road approach is where the media practice peace journalism with focus on reporting for conflict transformation. Peace Journalism as Galtung puts forward is reporting of conflicts where media explores the conflict formation, its causes and consequences; voice to all parties; focus on invisible effects of conflicts, uncover truths of all side and is people and solution oriented.

With the incidents of conflicts occurring across society's media's role in communicating conflict has been discussed widely by scholars and practitioners. The study builds its discussion on the premise that media use of war tactics to report news stories is against communication ethics. According to Galadima (2021) media plays a fundamental role in "communicating to the public what happens in the world. In those cases in which audiences do not possess direct knowledge or experience of what is happening, they become particularly reliant upon the media to inform them." Conflicts are tragedies that involve killings, bloodsheds, displacements, economic consequence and emotional turmoil. It is in media "conflicts are defined, framed and visualized; elaborated, narrativized and evaluated: moralized, deliberated and contested; amplified and promoted or dampened and reconciled" (Galadima, 2021). Ekström, Fornäs, Jansson, & Jerslev, (2016) regard mass media to be mirror of the society but a distorted one which implies a possibility that media's distorted representation could emphasize prejudice among the public. Media mediates reality and the way they mitigate becomes a major factor. Media's coverage of conflict has the potential to instigate conflicts as well as resolve conflicts. How and what media represents can shape people's perception to a great instance. Media outlets are being treated as "actors" within international conflicts capable of shaping and refining opinions (Al-Najjar, 2019). Journalism is a moral enterprise that creates public discourse and there exists ethical norms according to which media should report. "Ethics" is a set of concepts and principles that guide us in determining what behavior helps or harms sentient creatures. The chief purpose of codes of ethics is to impact journalists' actions – to enforce social responsibility. Peace journalism therefore, as conceptualized by Galtung (1998), advocates for a media approach to facilitate peaceful coexistence in the society. Peace journalism promote peace by framing news stories in ways that avoid inflaming conflicts and instead encourage dialogue, understanding, and resolution. Johan Galtung, who pioneered the concept, defines peace journalism as "when editors and reporters make choices about what to report, and how to report it that create opportunities for society at large to consider and value nonviolent responses to conflict" (Galtung, 1998). It contrasts with war journalism, which tends to be reactive, elite-focused, and violence-oriented. It focuses on identifying the causes of conflict, giving voice to all parties, particularly the marginalized, and highlighting peace initiatives. It seeks to deconstruct narratives that polarize and instead promote unity and constructive engagement (Lynch & McGoldrick, 2005).

Peace journalism is solution oriented other than the traditional war journalism which focused was on sensationalism. Lynch and McGoldrick (2005) argued that Peace journalism transient mere routine reporting but rather careful selection of a stylish technique that not only appeals to emotions but also encourages peaceful responses to conflict. In Nigeria today where most media content aggravate public unrest, peace journalism is a paradigm shift from that era.

One of the cardinal or ethics of journalistic practice is objective and balance, but this often times is not absolutely observed by journalists in terms of crisis. Peace journalism encourages reports that reduces conflicts rather than escalating it which some critics argued that doing that is a compromise to the ethics of the profession (Hanitzsch, 2007). However, peace journalism advocates for a clear balance between accuracy and peace.

Nigeria as a country that is religiously and culturally sensitive, requires journalists to strictly adhere to their ethics while reporting. Journalists therefore, are urged to be careful of stereotyping and usage of provocative language in their reportage. The Nigerian Press Council (NPC) Code of Ethics for Nigerian Journalists emphasizes the need for respect for cultural values and avoidance of hate speech (NPC, 2020).

Peace journalists are vested with the responsibility as part of their ethical provision of 'Responsibility and Accountability' to ponder on the consequences of their reportage. As part of their ethics, journalists should prioritize human dignity and be careful of reporting issues that are capable of inciting the society against themselves. Union leaders should also be watchful and hold accountable any journalist that is found wanting of such.

This paper therefore, is committed to exploring the legal and ethical contexts that regulates peace journalism in Nigeria, assessing how these contexts can be leverage to foster national cohesion and reduce conflict.

2. Conceptual Clarification

Peace Journalism: Peace journalism as adopted in this paper, is a journalistic approach that focuses on balance and objectivity when reporting on conflict and war, with the sole aim of fostering peace and strengthen understanding between the two conflicting parties rather than amplifying the conflict or violence. It prioritizes exploring root causes, seeking common ground between parties, and highlighting peaceful solutions. This is in agreement with Tehranian (2002) who conceptualized Peace journalism, as part of journalistic approach which seeks to promote and accentuates resolution, truth-telling, and narratives that prioritize human dignity.

Ethics : Ethics as adopted in this paper are principles that guide journalists often rooted in personal values, cultural norms, and societal expectations. This provides a framework for understanding what is right and wrong, and they are often based on moral philosophy. Ethical decision-making involves choosing between options, even when the answer is not clear-cut, and may involve conflicting principles like beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, and justice.

Law: Law as adopted in this paper, are set of rules established by a governing body and enforced by legal institutions to maintain social order in the society. Laws define what actions are legally permitted and prohibited, and they often involve consequences for non-compliance, such as fines, or imprisonment.

Legal: Legal as adopted in this paper is a system of rules that operates within a structured framework of laws that are enforced by recognized institutions.

3. Literature Review

The media is the lens through which the public receives data about what is happening around them and beyond. Journalists therefore, as the watchdogs of every society are vested with responsibility of performing surveillance function. In their judgment and selection of what becomes news, journalists and other media professionals are governed by news values (Olomofejobi, 2017). Among the numerous news values that the media considered very important was conflict. Conflict is key news value-driving media coverage. Peace journalism in Nigeria on the other operates within a complex landscape marked by ethical dilemmas and legal challenges. This literature review synthesizes key scholarly perspectives on the ethical and legal issues confronting peace journalism in the country. The issues include:

3.1 Ethical Issues in Peace Journalism

a. Framing and Identity Construction

Akinfeleye A A, Okoye E. O (2003) highlights a significant disconnection between media framing practices and professional ethics in Nigeria. Analyzing coverage of the farmer-herder crisis and the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) movement, the study reveals that Nigerian newspapers often employ negative frames and constructed identities, leaning more towards war and ethnic journalism rather than peace-oriented reporting. This approach contradicts the ethical principles outlined by the Nigerian Union of Journalists (NUJ) and underscores the need for socially responsible journalism practices.

b. Corruption and Conflict of Interest

Corruption within journalism, including practices like "brown envelope journalism," poses a significant ethical challenge to journalism profession

and of course peace journalism. This term refers to journalists accepting monetary or other incentives in exchange for favorable coverage or suppression of negative information. Such practices undermine journalistic integrity and independence, leading to biased reporting influenced by external interests. This kind of report insight and is capable of stirring public unrest especially if it is a conflict oriented report.

c. News Commercialization

[Ngantem and Dapiya \(2017\)](#) discuss the ethical implications of news commercialization in Nigeria. The intrusion of commercial interests into news content has compromised objectivity, accuracy, and fairness. Journalists often face pressure to produce content that aligns with the interests of advertisers or sponsors, leading to distorted news and imbalanced reporting. This commercialization trend erodes public trust and hampers the media's role in promoting peace in the society and informed discourse.

3.2 Legal Challenges in Peace Journalism

a. Regulatory Bodies and Press Freedom

The Nigerian Press Council (NPC), established by the Nigerian Press Council Act No. 85 of 1992 (as amended in Act 60 of 1999), serves as the statutory body governing ethical standards in the Nigerian press. While the NPC aims to uphold professional standards, its effectiveness is often questioned due to allegations of government interference and lack of autonomy. Such challenges hinder the enforcement of ethical practices and compromise press freedom.

b. Legal Risks and Censorship

Journalists in Nigeria face legal risks, including defamation lawsuits and censorship, particularly when reporting on sensitive issues like corruption and human rights violations. The case of *Punch Newspapers v. Nigerian Army (2020)* exemplifies these challenges, where the newspaper faced a defamation suit after reporting on alleged military abuses. Although the court ruled in favor of the newspaper, the case underscores the legal pressures journalists encounter.

c. Cybercrime Legislation and Digital Journalism

The Cybercrimes Act of 2015 presents additional legal challenges for journalists, especially those operating online. The Act has been used to suppress critical reporting and silence dissenting voices under the guise of combating cybercrime. This legal environment creates a chilling effect, discouraging investigative journalism and limiting the media's capacity to hold power to account.

4. Methodology

This article adopts desk research method which is also referred to as 'Secondary Research' which entails collecting and analyzing an already existing data. Unlike primary source of data collection which gathers its data from the field work or survey, desk research makes use of already published materials such as books, journals, documents and newspapers relating to the subject matter. This method is adopted to enhance and broaden the researcher's understanding on the subject matter. It also saves time and is cost-effective.

5. Discussion

Peace journalism in Nigeria operates within a complex framework of ethical obligations and legal constraints that shape how journalists report on conflict, violence, and societal tensions. The practice seeks to minimize harm, promote dialogue, and de-escalate conflict through responsible reporting. However, media professionals often encounter ethical dilemmas and legal challenges that affect their ability to effectively practice peace journalism.

5.1 Ethical Issues in Peace Journalism

One of the major ethical issues in peace journalism is the conflict between objectivity and advocacy. Peace journalism encourages journalists to frame stories in ways that foster understanding and reconciliation rather than exacerbating conflict. However, this may be perceived as biased or agenda-driven by traditional journalistic standards that emphasize neutrality ([Lynch & McGoldrick, 2005](#)). In Nigeria, where ethnic, religious, and political divides are sensitive and deeply rooted, journalists often struggle to maintain balance while still promoting peace. Another concern is the use of inflammatory language or stereotypes. In regions plagued by communal

violence, such as Kaduna or Plateau States, some media outlets have been criticized for using sensational headlines or ethnic identifiers that escalate tensions ([Akinfeleye, 2003](#)). Ethical journalism demands restraint and cultural sensitivity, yet economic pressures and competition for readership sometimes lead to compromise in these areas.

Journalists also face challenges with verifying sources in conflict zones. The urgency to report breaking news often results in the dissemination of unverified or biased information. Ethically, journalists are expected to cross-check facts and avoid spreading rumors, but access limitations and the politicization of information can make this difficult in Nigeria's volatile media landscape.

5.2 Legal Issues in Peace Journalism

Legally, peace journalists in Nigeria operate under ambiguous and sometimes repressive laws that can stifle freedom of expression. The Nigerian Constitution (Section 39) guarantees freedom of the press, but this right is often undermined by laws such as the Cybercrimes Act (2015), the Criminal Code, and the Nigeria Broadcasting Code, which have been used to prosecute or silence journalists under the guise of national security or public order (*Media Rights Agenda, 2021*).

The lack of legal protection for whistleblowers and investigative journalists also discourages the reporting of truth in sensitive conflict situations. Moreover, media practitioners frequently face harassment, intimidation, or arrest by security agencies for publishing reports perceived as critical of the government or powerful interests, particularly during election cycles or civil unrest. The issue of ownership influence further complicates legal and ethical boundaries. Many Nigerian media houses are owned by politicians or business moguls, which can lead to editorial bias and censorship. Journalists may be pressured to suppress reports that portray their sponsors negatively, even if those reports are essential to peace-building efforts.

6. Conclusion

Nigeria's socio-political scenery is fraught with conflicts ranging from religious insurgencies in the North to communal clashes in the South. The media, as a vital stakeholder in nation-building, plays a crucial role in either exacerbating or alleviating tensions ([Umaru & Abdullahi, 2019](#)). Peace journalism a framework that aims to report conflicts in ways that promote peace has been advocated as a solution. However, ethical and legal challenges often undermine its effectiveness is the order of the day in journalistic practice in Nigeria. This situation which presents unique ethical and legal hurdles necessitate a strong localized framework for peace journalism practice. Journalists of both broadcast, print and digital media should be peace oriented when reporting conflict especially those of cross-border nature. Particularly where the government of the day embraces a non-violent disposition in conflict resolution, the journalists should back up such approach without sentiments.

7. Recommendations

Having critically examine the topic 'Ethical and legal issues guiding peace journalism in Nigeria' the following way forward are recommended:

- i. Multi-pronged approach which include institutional modifications, a periodic and mandatory legal refresher training and ethical capacity building be organized where all journalists' knowledge will be refreshed on the professional tenets and ethical reporting to avoid ethical and legal misconduct.
- ii. Journalists welfare must be as a matter of urgency and necessity be reviewed and revamp to avoid to case of accepting brown envelop syndrome.
- iii. National Union of Journalists (NUJ) must strive very hard to ensure that all media outfits regain their Editorial Independence to avoid external interference thereby resulting to ethical and legal issues in peace journalism.
- iv. Furthermore, international standards such as those set by UNESCO and Reporters Without Borders offer frameworks that can help Nigerian journalists align with global best practices in peace journalism, even within restrictive local environments.
- v. NUJ must also as a matter of necessity strive to equip journalists especially those in to peace journalism with the necessary tools and protection to function or practice ethically, legally and responsibly.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Journalists can function effectively and sufficiently as catalyst for peace in Nigeria's complex socio-political environment if the afore mentioned recommendations will be judiciously and painstakingly followed.

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